

QUALITY OF SERVICE (QOS) IN CAMPUS NETWORK: COMPREHENSIVE SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Currently many aspects of the classical architecture of the Internet are extensively well-known, which has led to major obstacles in internet services. At present, there exist many reasons to extend the Internet including providing end-to-end connectivity for users, allowing Quality of Service (QoS) management of network resources for new applications, such as data center, cloud computing, and network virtualization. Defining those parameters and causes which affect on internet services especially the QoS and developing significant ant techniques to solve them is continued to be a major challenge. Although developers, researchers, and scholars from different countries abroad have introduced and proposed numerous solutions to solve the QoS drawbacks of the recent networking, numbers of them are failed or were not implemented. Furthermore, many recent types of research have addressed the QoS in campus network and introduce new concepts toward QoS improvements such as the Software Defined Networking (SDN) in modern-generation architecture, the deployment of control plane software components (e.g., OpenFlow controller), and more. A critical understanding of the Quality of Service (QoS) in campus network obstacles is necessary to address the multiple challenges and realizing the QoS future development. To address these challenges and available solutions this paper review some existing techniques of QoS in campus network which is related targeted goals of QoS future development in the campus network.

Keywords: Future Internet, Quality of Service (QoS), campus network, Software-Defined Networking (SDN), OpenFlow controller

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the explosive growth of real-time applications that require stringent Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees, brings the network programmers to design network protocols that deliver certain performance guarantees. While, with the huge and rapid advance of a computer network, the structure of the campus network is the inescapable choice of the improvement of the information network. The campus network framework is quite large and complicated system. It is not only for modern teaching, integrated information management and office automation series of applications to provide a basic operating platform, but also to provide a variety of application services, so that information can be timely and accurate delivery. The campus network construction in the application of network technology is the important branch of LAN technology to build and management [1]. The capacity of the current Internet with rapid growth is becoming insufficient to carry the large volumes of traffic patterns delivered by the new services and modalities, where new types of networking services are appeared and generated for a huge number of end users. Specifically, the currently utilized infrastructure system of the network has been preserved almost in the same structure for decades, while technology continues to evolve. Resource management is of paramount importance in network scenarios and it is a long-standing and still open issue. Where the existing networks have built with multiple stages of static Ethernet switches organized in a tree structure are not sufficient for the dynamic computing and storage needs of today's carrier environments and future developments. The improvement of the network speedup, scalability, and robustness with the effective creation and delivery of versatile digital services that provide stringent Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees is a key demand. However, all of these services and applications require different treatments for their own owns to make the delivery successful over a network (e.g. some applications such as video conferencing require a certain bandwidth for its flow, other applications are sensitive to the delay over a network, and more other specific requirements. Thus, defining these needs a well-understanding Quality of Service (QoS) mechanism(s) in a network is a unique term [2].

One significant solution that has paid attention until the recent time is SDN. The SDN isolates network control from data and information transfer. As a result, filtering, routing algorithms, firewalls and other more algorithms utilized in various elements of the network are transferred to switches and controller solely transfer the data. Therefore, with particular help of this architecture, the networks become more controllable and smarter, their dependence on hardware is decreased and their management will become simpler and more flexible, while their Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees. Eventually, The objective of the present paper is to get a clear understanding for the Quality of Service (QoS) in campus network obstacles which necessary to address the multiple challenges and realizing the QoS future development for campus networks uses. The effect is represented by attention to the architecture of these networks in which control and the Service (QoS) in the campus network.

RELATED STUDY

Several studies have been done in prior works on Quality of Service (QoS) in the campus network. A novel approach to stream video over OpenFlow networks with QoS has been investigated and contacted by [3], it fulfilled end-to-end QoS support which is possible with OpenFlow's centralized control capabilities over the network. A new scheduling and channel allocation mechanisms have been proposed that ensure QoS for IMM applications over WCNs is introduced by [4]. The proposed mechanism delivers QoS with the least handoff delay and minimizes the call dropping probabilities. A QoS-based Network Virtualization technique has been presented by [5]. The technique is based on constraint placement language used when mapping virtual network (node and links) over the substrate infrastructure which significantly ensures QoS requirements of application flows. Another approach of the new mechanism (WiFi AP) has been developed by [6]. The mechanism based on (WiFi AP) has been studied in different protocols in wireless networks and focused on the WLAN IEEE 802.11. The problem associated with our current WiFi is too much delay and loss of packets. The proposed (WiFi AP) has been conducted to enhance the QoS of the wireless network including delay and loss. However, this study does not provide sufficient results and evaluation to support system performance which left as future work.

Another performed work on using SDN for video flow handling can be seen in [7], where a QoS Controller (Q-Ctrl) system is used to control and allocate bandwidth for the virtual machines supporting video streaming in a cloud infrastructure. The proposed approach aims to achieve QoS in an SDN based cloud infrastructure. While it is more efficient in wide-area and WAMI data visualization. A mobile application which developed to gather the metrics necessary to evaluate QoE in a mobile environment over the network on campus is presented by [8]. This prototype application is able to evaluate the user perceived QoE in various Internet services. However, the mean opinion score (MOS) of the proposed approach does not consider the jitter, packet-loss and signal strength. A new mechanism to improve the QoS by reducing the IP packet delay is proposed by [9]. The mechanisms are analyzed through a simple packet transfer simulator that offers different combinations of mechanisms to be used in the simulation, allowing different packet transfer scenario setups. However, the proposed approach comes with a simple design which needs to be improved by adding new QoS mechanisms to show the individual and combined effects QoS on packet transfer.

A distributed QoS-oriented model for the improvement of network performance for fixed WiMAX using QoS parameters is introduced by [10].

The method improved the of the point-to-point system of delivering bandwidth from central server to WiMAX BSs and SSs. However, the coverage area of WiMAX needs to be increased. A campus SWAN architecture in order to provide quality of service (QoS) guarantees to the campus WLAN users is presented by [11]. The SWAN is decoupled into a control plane and data plane which led to network control for a large number of Aps. In [12] a QoS of video conferencing between main campus and sub-campus as the implementation of a distance learning system is presented. The outcomes results show that the system is able to achieve sufficient results of bandwidth, jitter, and packet loss. While it does not consider the QoS in the access, distribution, and core levels where video/audio traffic pass-through. A new technique to provide a scalable yet efficient solution to distributed SDN network management is proposed by [13]. It is an architecture as a collaborative multi-domain to load balancing and network performance enhancement in software-defined networks. The author also introduced a distributed machine learning agent to allow controllers to evaluate which brokers are more advantageous than other. While it is required to modify the Flow Broker to provide better scalability and to avoid the scenario in which a single layer of brokering actually increases overhead.

A role-based SDN campus network slicing approach has been proposed by [14]. The approach involves with authentication controller and the virtualization technology of Flow-Visor which led to reduce the flow setup latency 14% to 60% compared to that of MAC-based slicing. While the proposed approach is required to be applicable in real campus networks to efficiently manage them. A technique for stitching inter-domain paths under the control of centralized routing brokers which known as IXPs has been introduced by [15], it allows for providing paths with end-to-end guarantees for mission-critical applications. A new technique which known as an open northbound API has been proposed by [16]. The method is enables streaming video applications to easily enforce Quality of Service (QoS) requirements in a high-level fashion, without incurring any controller's code coupling or network operator intervention. However, the approach needs to be integrated with other OpenFlow controllers beyond to better support its communication between a single streaming video application and disparate SDN controllers. Another technique of Bandwidth-allocation controller which called (NN-SPID) is developed by [17]. The proposed technique is based on PID control strategy to control QoS requirements relying on an auto-adaptive neural network to ensures the minimum guaranteed bandwidth levels to users according to their contracted SLA, and it also shows more stability and robustness than GA-SPID. However, The proposed technique does not consider on controlling other QoS parameters such as jitter, packet delay of sensitive traffic, or packet loss ratio. In [18] new Scheduling algorithms for evaluating the performance of QoS over MPLS/VPN/WiMAX networks has been presented. Based on the proposed scheduling algorithms, it clearly observed that MWRR has the lowest delay in both VPN and WiMAX. However, the long-term Evolution advanced (LTE-adv) networks have not been achieved yet.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Technique	Contribution and drawbacks	Reference
An OpenFlow controller design	A novel approach to stream video over OpenFlow networks with QoS, it fulfilled end-to-end QoS support which is possible with OpenFlow's centralized control capabilities over the network.	[3]
Scheduling mechanism for IMM applications	A new scheduling and channel allocation mechanisms that ensure QoS for IMM applications over WCNs. It delivers QoS with the least handoff delay and minimizes the call dropping probabilities.	[4]
QoS-based Network Virtualization	A constraint placement language used when mapping virtual network (node and links) over the substrate infrastructure to ensure QoS requirements of application flows.	[5]
Optimized Routing in OpenFlow Networks	Streaming setup that utilizes the flexible routing possibilities provided by an SDN implemented with OpenFlow. It improves the QoS by changing the metric model of the Dijkstra algorithm.	[19]
QoS control and SRTP for real-time multimedia streaming	Quality of Service (QoS) control and Secure Real-time Transport Protocol (SRTP) approach to provide a smooth streaming under various network bandwidths, while maintaining effective security.	[20]
A novel SHRP strategy	A novel QoS routing strategy called Swarm-based Hybrid Routing Protocol (SHRP) which able to select the minimum delay path with the maximum available bandwidth at nodes	[21]
A new mechanism of (WIFI AP)	Enhance the QoS of the wireless network including delay and loss. However, the study does not conduct clear results and evaluation to support system performance which left as future work.	[6]

Q-Ctrl system for video flow handling	Achieving high QoS in an SDN based cloud infrastructure. While it is more efficient in wide-area and WAMI data visualization.	[7]
A (QoE) evaluation model	A prototype application that evaluates the user perceived QoE in various Internet services over a mobile network in the campus. While its mean opinion score (MOS) does not consider the jitter, packet-loss and signal strength parameters.	[8]
A new QoS mechanisms	A new mechanism to improve the QoS by reducing the IP packet delay. While the proposed approach comes with a simple design which needs to be improved by adding new QoS mechanisms to show the individual and combined effects QoS on packet transfer.	[9]
Distributed QoS-oriented model	Improvement of network performance for fixed WiMAX using QoS parameters. the method improved the of the point-to-point system of delivering bandwidth from central server to WiMAX BSs and SSs. However, the coverage area of WiMAX needs to be increased.	[10]
A new campus SWAN architecture	A new campus WLAN architecture based on the concept of SDN called as SWAN. The SWAN is decoupled into a control plane and data plane which led to network control for a large number of APs	[11]
Real-time QoS-Aware video streaming	Performance evaluation for video transmission over LAN using Data Distribution Service (DDS). The proposed DDS consumes low bandwidth, has low jitter and causes lesser packet loss. While the examination for the QoS parameters to come up with the best configuration has not been contacted.	[22]
Allocation algorithm with Xen and Linux QoS	An allocation algorithm combined with Xen and Linux QoS which able to achieve the dynamic control of network bandwidth and flexibility to adjust the allocation scheme.	[23]
Flow Broker architecture	Multi-domain approach to load balancing and network performance enhancement in software-defined networks. It minimizes the maximum link utilization that leads to link saturation and significant packet loss. While it needs to be modified for Flow Broker to provide better scalability.	[13]

A fine granular API for QoS configuration	A QoS configuration API at the SDNC approach, its outcomes demonstrate the efficient capabilities of the QoS Config AP and give an indication about its significant performance. however, the SDNC needs to be extended with higher level abstractions.	[24]
A novel software-defined automatic QoS management	This model provides a universal scheme for autonomic network management in SDN with high effectiveness. The model does not other QoS parameters including jitter and loss.	[25]
Trust DSCP model for QoS evaluation	A video conference system testing for distance learning between two campuses with achieving sufficient results of bandwidth, jitter, and packet loss. While it doesn't consider the QoS in the access, distribution, and core levels where video traffic pass-through.	[12]
Open Cache API	An interface for developers and users which uses SDN-based technology to provide the redirection functionality necessary for a cache to perform effectively.	[26]
Role-based SDN campus network slicing	Involves with authentication controller and the virtualization technology of Flow-Visor which led to reduce the flow setup latency. While the proposed approach is required to be applicable in real campus networks to efficiently manage them.	[14]
IXPs	Technique for stitching inter-domain paths under the control of centralized routing brokers, which provide paths with end-to-end guarantees for mission-critical applications.	[15]
Bandwidth-allocation controller (NN-SPID)	Ensures the minimum guaranteed bandwidth levels to users depending on their service level agreement. However, the proposed technique does not consider on controlling other QoS parameters such as jitter, packet delay, or packet loss ratio.	[17]
Open northbound API	Enables streaming video applications to easily and achieving QoS goals without having to struggle with low-level OpenFlow instructions. However, it needs to be integrated with other OpenFlow controllers beyond to better support its communication.	[16]
New scheduling algorithms	Scheduling algorithms for evaluating the performance of QoS over MPLS/VPN/WiMAX networks. While long-term	[18]

	Evolution advanced (LTE-adv) networks have not been achieved.	
Flexible 5G architecture for network slicing	Extensions for NFV orchestration that provide network slice tailored support for mobility and QoS, while ensuring efficient utilization of the substrate network resources. However, there are still open points in the algorithm definitions.	[27]

QoS models Technique	Hard Quality of Service (QoS)				Soft Quality of Service (QoS)			
	Bandwidth	Delay	Jitter	Loss	Bandwidth	Delay	Jitter	Loss
New (WIFI AP) mechanism						√		√
Bandwidth controller (NN-SPID)	√				√			
Q-Ctrl system for video flow handling	√				√			
Open northbound API	√	√						
Flow Broker architecture	√	√		√	√	√		√
Role-based SDN campus network slicing						√		
IXPs					√	√		
A (QoE) evaluation model					√	√		
Trust CoS model and Trust DSCP for QoS evaluation					√		√	√
A new QoS mechanisms						√		

Distributed QoS-oriented Model					√	√		
A fine granular API for QoS configuration						√		
A novel software-defined automatic QoS management model	√	√			√	√		
Scheduling mechanism for IMM applications					√	√		
New scheduling algorithms						√	√	
A new campus SWAN architecture					√			
QoS-based Network Virtualization					√	√		
Real-time QoS-Aware video streaming					√		√	√
A framework for automatic QoS control	√				√			
Open Cache API					√	√		
Optimized Routing in OpenFlow Networks					√	√		
QoS control and SRTP for multimedia streaming					√	√		

Allocation algorithm with Xen and Linux QoS					√			
Flexible 5G architecture for network slicing					√	√		
A novel SHRP strategy					√	√		

DISCUSSION

Based on the evaluations of techniques, methods, and algorithms detailed in this paper, one could conclude that most of the solutions involving network applications, software-defined networks with Quality of Service (QoS) guaranty for campus network and other related areas contribute to the quality of service significantly. The effect of software-defined networks on quality of service of applications is inevitable. Wthe considering the routing methods and metrics used in each of them, one may infer that some novel software techniques and other methods based on Flow Broker architectures are suitable for Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees in networks. In addition, tables above offers a comparison between the most significant methods suggested in the present paper for use of campus networks and other related applications that could be adopted.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the main problems of the today networks is the ability to manage differentiating services guaranteeing the various QoS requirements. Thus, in the present paper, some most recent architectures and methods for offering the required Quality of Service (QoS) in campus networks and other related applications in current networks are contacted and reviewed. Then, contribution, drawback problems of these methods were contacted. The effect is represented by attention to the architecture of these networks in which control and guaranty the Quality of Service (QoS) in the campus network. We can conclude also that SDN and OpenFlow will most likely become pervasive technologies in the future networks since they have an enormous potential contribution in a large number of different applications and fields. In addition, for QoS in networks, the lack of sufficient bandwidth, as well as high packet loss or delay, can impact very negatively on the quality of service. Finally, more work and focus is needed toward an efficient Quality of Service (QoS) in campus network and related applications is control and guaranty.

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